

How Reliable Are Global Traffic Volume Estimates for Crash Hotspot Identification?

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Abstract. Crash hotspot identification requires normalizing crash counts by traffic exposure, yet measured Annual Average Daily Traffic (AADT) data are sparse in most countries. Machine-learning models that predict AADT globally from open geospatial data promise to close this gap, but whether their predictions are accurate enough for safety applications has not been tested on data outside the training set. We present the first cross-national external validation of such a global AADT model, comparing its predictions against 22,939 ground-truth measurements from four countries, and then propagate the resulting AADT uncertainty through crash rates using Monte Carlo simulation on 1.4 million geocoded crashes. Absolute crash-rate uncertainty is large (a factor of 14–28 between the 5th and 95th percentiles), but *relative* hotspot rankings hold up moderately well ($\rho = 0.71\text{--}0.83$). Even so, only about 3–19% of the nominally top-10% hotspots (0.3–1.9% of all segments) stay consistently classified across all uncertainty realizations. Together, these results give practitioners the first evidence-based guidance on when global AADT predictions are, and are not, good enough for road safety screening.

Submission Type. Analysis, Case Study

BoK Concepts. [AM11] Network Analysis, [AM7] Spatial statistics, [GD4] Data quality

Keywords. traffic volume estimation, AADT, crash hotspot identification, uncertainty propagation, road safety, spatial validation

1 Introduction

Road traffic crashes kill roughly 1.19 million people every year (World Health Organization, 2023). Identifying crash hotspots (road segments with disproportionately high crash risk) is a cornerstone of evidence-based road safety management (AASHTO, 2010; Persaud et al.,

1999), and doing so means normalizing crash counts by traffic exposure, which in turn means having segment-level estimates of Annual Average Daily Traffic (AADT) (AASHTO, 2010). The trouble is that measured AADT data are expensive to collect and spatially sparse, and the regions most in need of safety screening often have the least traffic data.

Recently, van Strien and Grêt-Regamey (2024) released a global AADT model: a Quantile Random Forest trained on open geospatial data that predicts AADT, with 90% prediction intervals, for 3.3 million extra-urban road segments across 222 countries. These predictions could in principle serve as a universal denominator for crash-rate computation, but are they accurate enough for safety-critical decisions? AADT errors have well-documented consequences for safety analysis (Lord and Miranda-Moreno, 2008; Zarei and Hellinga, 2023), yet no study has empirically tested whether the uncertainty in such global AADT predictions propagates into meaningful distortions in crash hotspot rankings. We address this gap through three linked analyses: (1) a cross-national external validation of the predictions against independent ground truth, (2) Monte Carlo propagation of AADT uncertainty through crash rates, and (3) an assessment of hotspot ranking stability against both ground-truth and naive baselines.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Ground-Truth AADT and Crash Data

We use measured AADT from Germany (12,089 counts, 2021), the UK (21,645; 2022), France (3,741; 2019), and California (13,854; 2022), spatially matched within 25 m to the predicted segments using a tight point-to-line protocol with road-class and bearing sanity gates. This yields 22,939 deduplicated segment-level pairs. We then assembled 1.4 million geocoded crashes (2021–2022) from national databases (German Unfallatlas, UK STATS19,

French BAAC, California CCRS), snapped them within 100 m to segments, and converted counts into crashes per 100 million vehicle-kilometers.

2.2 Uncertainty Propagation and Hotspot Stability

For each segment, we assume a log-normal AADT distribution parameterized by its prediction interval. This choice preserves the reported 5th and 95th quantiles of the nonparametric Quantile Random Forest intervals and enforces positivity; a log-Student- t sensitivity check shifts the stable-hotspot fractions by less than 0.2 percentage points. To characterize per-segment uncertainty, we draw 5,000 (AADT, crash-count) pairs per segment, sampling AADT from the log-normal fit to the prediction interval and crash counts from a Poisson distribution centered on the observed count, and then summarize each segment's crash-rate distribution. Hotspot-ranking stability is assessed in a separate 1,000-iteration pass that perturbs all segments jointly: in each iteration we draw one (AADT, crash-count) realization for every segment, rank segments by crash rate, and flag the top 10%. Segments appearing in the top 10% in more than 80% of iterations are classified as *stable hotspots*, 20–80% as *borderline*, and less than 20% as *stable non-hotspots*. Finally, we benchmark rankings against ground-truth-based crash rates using Spearman correlation and top- K % Jaccard similarity.

2.3 Data and Software Availability

All traffic volume data come from national transport authorities (BASt, DfT, DGITM, Caltrans) and the crash data from publicly accessible government databases (Unfallatlas, STATS19, BAAC, CCRS). The global AADT predictions are available from van Strien and Grêt-Regamey (2024). The analysis code will be released alongside the forthcoming journal publication to support transparency and reproducibility.

3 Results

Validation. The global model achieves a log-scale R^2 of 0.421–0.660 across the four countries (California highest, France lowest), notably below the 0.74 reported from internal cross-validation. AADT-level Spearman correlations sit between 0.73 and 0.83, which suggests that relative traffic-volume ordering is preserved better than absolute magnitudes. Prediction interval coverage (0.78–0.92) falls below the nominal 90% target in three of four countries, and drops further to 0.43–0.54 for low-volume roads (below 2,000 AADT), where MdAPE exceeds 200%. In Germany, the UK, and California, these low-volume segments are systematically overestimated.

Crash Rate Uncertainty. Monte Carlo propagation reveals median uncertainty ratios of 14–28 \times (95th/5th percentile), meaning a typical segment's crash rate could

plausibly vary by more than an order of magnitude. This uncertainty reflects both the breadth of the AADT prediction intervals and the inherent stochasticity of crash counts.

Hotspot Stability. Despite this large absolute uncertainty, *relative* rankings are moderately preserved: Spearman $\rho = 0.71$ – 0.83 and a top-10% Jaccard of 0.31–0.50, far above the random-expectation baseline of 0.053. Under the strict persistence criterion (more than 80% of draws), only 0.3–1.9% of *all* segments remain stably classified as hotspots (0.04–0.67% under a Negative Binomial crash-count model with $k = 2$). That is equivalent to roughly 3–19% of the nominal top-10% surviving AADT uncertainty; a further 14–18% fall into the borderline zone, and the rest are stable non-hotspots. European countries show better agreement with ground truth than California does.

Value of AADT Normalization. Rankings based on the global AADT predictions substantially outperform naive baselines: raw crash count yields $\rho = 0.11$ – 0.35 and crash density $\rho = 0.45$ – 0.73 , confirming that even noisy AADT normalization adds meaningful information.

Coverage Gap. The global model covers only extra-urban roads, capturing just 21–48% of crashes depending on the country. The remaining crashes occur on urban and local roads, precisely where crash densities are highest.

4 Conclusions

This study provides the first empirical assessment of global AADT predictions for crash hotspot identification. The model is *suitable for screening-level* corridor identification on extra-urban roads similar to the validated subset (top-20% Jaccard 0.41–0.55), but *insufficient for segment-level resource allocation* (top-5% Jaccard 0.24–0.47). The systematic overestimation of low-volume roads is particularly concerning, since it can mask genuine hotspots on rural roads. Future work should extend this validation to low- and middle-income countries, where safety needs are greatest.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author used Anthropic's Claude (Opus 4.6 and Opus 4.5) for language editing, copy-editing, and coding assistance during analysis and manuscript preparation. The author reviewed and verified all outputs and takes full responsibility for the scientific content, data, and conclusions of this work.

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